

A psychological framework for robotic personality

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Abstract—This study introduces a novel approach to enhance human-robot interaction through robotic personalities. Based on the Big Five factor model, a taxonomy model is presented to synthesize personalities. The core of this framework leverages a Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model, enabling tailored behaviors for each personality trait. Empirical validation uses a pilot experiment with participants interacting with a robot that embodies different personalities. Questionnaire analysis confirms the framework’s effective creation of well-perceived personality dimensions.

Index Terms—synthetic personalities, Social Robotics, Human-Robot Interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Can the psychological dimensions of synthetic personalities be perceivable by humans? This research question guides the implementation of a robotic framework for synthetic personalities presented within this work. Personalities have a significant influence on human behavior and thoughts. Consequently, it plays a crucial role in shaping interactions between individuals. Psychologists have sought to simplify this concept by defining it through taxonomies, with the widely adopted Big Five Factor model being one such attempt [1]. The complexity of this concept is mirrored by fragmented literature in the field of social robotics, where a complete taxonomy of synthetic personalities does not exist. On the other hand, the necessity of introducing synthetic personalities is shown by recent research works. These have highlighted how carefully designing the robot’s personality may lead to more engaging, acceptable, likable, and trustable interaction [2], [3], [4].

Recent research acknowledges the potential of synthetic personalities in Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) but lacks evidence due to limited exploration of traits. The predominant focus on extroversion and the use of rule-based techniques for predefined personalities are limitations. This work aims to overcome these limitations, proposing a Big Five Factor-based taxonomy for social robots. Unlike existing approaches, the robot’s personality becomes an integral internal component, influencing all aspects of behavior, bridging perception, action, and planning. The framework’s ability to manage multiple personality dimensions concurrently sets it apart, and its generalizability extends to various tasks and robotic platforms.

II. METHODS

The study aims to create a broadly applicable personality model and introduces a platform-agnostic framework (Figure

Fig. 1. Personality-based software architecture. Three different modules can be identified: perception (left), reasoning (center), and actions (right).

1) composed of perception, action, and reasoning components. The central element is the Personality Generator module, which plays a pivotal role in the architecture and is founded on the concept of personality.

We introduced the CEA (Conscientiousness, Extroversion, Agreeableness) taxonomy, based on the three corresponding traits of the Big Five model. Humans shape robotic personalities using only these three dimensions [5] and are capable of distinguishing between only 4 and 8 personalities [6]. Personality is defined as a point within the three dimensional of the CEA taxonomy, as shown below:

$$Personality = W_e E + W_a A + W_c C \quad (1)$$

Where $E, A,$ and C correspond to the versors of the three axes namely Extroversion, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness. $W_e, W_a,$ and W_c are the length of the three one-dimensional vectors and denote how much a specific trait is expressed, giving the possibility of modeling personalities capturing the complexity of the psychological construct. Starting from this definition of synthetic personality, the framework is mainly based on a component capable to reproduce the activity of the human psychological construct, i.e., to be able of affecting the robot’s behavior in all its facets: language, vocal cues (pitch, volume, velocity), gaze, head movements, gestures (amplitude and velocity), and navigation (speed, proximity). All these behavioral features have been explored starting from relevant literature in the psychological field, leading to the definition of the Personality Generator module, which needs

to be capable of predicting the behavior of the robot given an action to execute and a personality trait. For this purpose, a BERT attention-based architecture [7] has been fine-tuned on a developed dataset through the Huggingface API. This model learns the behavioral parameters that are required to execute an action given the robot’s personality. Within a single prediction, it can be pervasive within all the aspects of the robot’s behavior. This solution has the great advantage of being task- and platform-independent. Even if the actions generated by the planner are usually platform-specific, the BERT model learns a reduced representation of each specific action and still produces a set of parameters that applies to that specific personality. During each iteration, the planner outputs an action. A trait is randomly extracted from the normalized distribution of weights (eq. (1)). The behavioral parameters are generated and updated before executing the action.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Fig. 2. Experimental setup

The architecture has been validated on a collaborative task with the Pepper robot. This platform has been chosen since it presents all the capabilities required to explore all the personality-affected behaviors. To limit the number of personalities to test during the experiments for each trait the two extreme poles are used. Each pole is then combined with all the poles of the other two traits resulting in 12 personalities. 12 subjects take part in the collaborative construction of a tower of blocks with the Pepper robot shown in figure 2. Each participant takes part in two trials, resulting in 24 trials, where each pole has been experienced 8 times.

During the interaction, humans are sitting near a table with a series of blocks scattered upon it. The robot enters the room where the subject is and approaches them. The robot is required to briefly chitchat with the subject, asking them to build a tower of colored blocks, by providing specific instructions. Here, it provides orders one by one, moving to the next instruction when the user touches it on the head. When all instructions are over, the robot says goodbye and leaves the room. The specific order in which the robot’s actions

are executed is decided by the planner. The Italian validated version of 10 items Big Five Inventory [8], appropriately reversed to the third person to measure the perceived robot’s personality, has been administered to subjects at the end of each interaction.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The framework’s capability to generate synthetic personalities perceivable by users was assessed through separate experiments, where the same level of a trait was given as input for statistical comparison. The Mann-Whitney U test was used with the displayed pole of the robot as the independent variable and the result obtained for that trait as the dependent variable. The p-values for Agreeableness and Extroversion ($p < 0.001$, $p = 0.001$) confirmed that two poles of the same trait are perceived as distinct. For Conscientiousness, the p-value was $p = 0.1$, suggesting a noticeable difference between conscientious and unscrupulous robots. To sum up, by modulating the three traits the human properly perceives a difference of the robot personality. Further analysis shows that CEA traits are not correlated hence chosen dimensions are not redundant in describing synthetic personality. These results suggest interesting insights that may be considered to optimize the Parameter Generator module and confirm that the proposed three-dimensional (CEA, i.e., Consciousness, Extroversion, Agreeableness) model for synthetic personality may be suitable for common HRI applications.

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